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Executive Summary

This document is the deliverable D1.3 “A strategy forward document describing the way forward towards an integrated EU Research Infrastructure”. It first establishes the ins and outs of marine data and information quality and presents how the establishment of an extended marine metrology infrastructure would contribute to overcoming the observed limitations.

MINKE proposes to leverage the standing situation by pooling and offering a full expertise in measurement and metrology. The initial key elements for the establishment of such an infrastructure, such as its values, missions, and vision, are shared. Finally, the first steps in building the business plan are presented with the metrology activities that can be provided.

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Introduction

This document is MINKE’s Deliverable 1.3 entitled “A strategy forward document describing the way forward towards an integrated EU Research Infrastructure”. The deliverable supports the objectives of WP1 of the project labelled “Building the Community” in its Document of Action. The aim of WP1 is to design the European transnational network focusing on the expanded metrology concept developed in MINKE for marine observations, particularly in Europe, that will bring together national metrology institutions, oceanographic research institutes, instrument manufacturers, relevant accreditation and standardisation bodies, marine data and service providers from the private and public sectors, and civil society.

Despite the acknowledged importance of marine observations in recent years, metrology concepts are rarely discussed in marine observing circles and in the marine data management community, notwithstanding its intimate link to sensor performance, data quality and control, and data usability issues.

MINKE’s vision incorporates the different layers, and linked disciplines, from the original measurements (complemented with metadata) to the full comprehension of the process under study, as depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1. Measurement-Comprehension pathway envisioned in MINKE

MINKE’s vision is new in that it is framed within a quintuple helix model of innovation that includes the natural environmental context (in this case, ocean health and sustainability) along with civil society (Non Governmental Organizations, makers communities, social media and citizen science platforms), academia, industry and governments in the backdrop shaping effective monitoring network designs.

Figure 2. Quintuple helix model of innovation, incorporating the natural environmental context (ocean health), civil society (NGO, makers community, social media and citizen science platforms), academia, industry and governments as the actors involved in monitoring the network design

The project focuses on sensitive and fundamental issues to improve data and information quality and related work behaviours and practices in marine monitoring networks, especially those operating transnationally and across multiple knowledge domains. Its goal is to outline how to build a sustainable regional framework in Europe that will serve as a permanent support to actions and initiatives aimed at improving the reliability and, most importantly, the usability of marine measurements, particularly in the long-term.

The actual MINKE network is still young but it is unique in the current marine research and monitoring landscape owing to its *raison d'être* which is, simply speaking, measurement, i.e., the process underlying (and conditioning the usability of) all data as well as any information obtained from them. While the MINKE project has managed to bring together the right people, resources and skills needed for dealing with such a central topic into a self-aware community for the first time, there is a need to ensure that this is only the first step and that the community continues to be nurtured so that it can reach its full potential.

One way to do this is to pursue a path towards the establishment of a full-fledged “MINKE” Research Infrastructure (RI) based on MINKE project’s accomplishments. As mentioned in the deliverable MINKE consortium D4.5 (2023), creating a distributed RI means that no single party is required to support and/or offer the complete range of

expertise, facilities, equipment, and services that are needed in the long term: a very wise approach to adopt seeing the quite obvious impracticability otherwise.

Furthermore, this would permit better chances of obtaining consistent funding by national and European funding authorities for this purpose. Overall, the enhanced stability that results from regular funding will empower the marine measurement quality value chain.

Consistent funding could also lead to coherent joint development plans for the optimization of an increasingly variegated suite of resources in the future, perhaps even employing alternative financial instruments like, for example, co-funding intelligently.

The proposed deliverable is a compilation of the work realised during the MINKE project aiming to describe the way forward towards an integrated EU RI.

In order to continue to strengthen the foundations of the community for the innovative “quality of oceanographic data and information” framework, common “Mission, Vision, Values” and “Strategy” were discussed at the “Strategic Development Programme for MINKE” workshop organized in Milano in 2024; partners exchanged their feedback and contributed, with many ideas, emerging for the definition of a future RI.

The first part of this document shows the actual Ocean observing landscape, highlighting the strengths and needs in terms of data quality requirements. Then, the second and final parts examine the strategy forward to progress towards the establishment of an integrated EU RI dedicated to marine metrology which could fulfill the metrology expectations identified.

1. Context

1.1 Ocean observation

Ocean observations are crucial for discovering unexplored parts of the Ocean, and to better observe, monitor and predict the physics, chemistry, biology and geology of the Ocean from global to coastal scales, and at appropriate temporal and spatial scales. The pivotal role of ocean observations has been identified in the UN Ocean Decade as a specific challenge (CH17 Sustainably Expand the Global Ocean Observing System) supporting and facilitating progress towards the 2030 goals (Miloslavich, P. et al, 2024). This is needed to better understand and predict climate change and its impacts on global Ocean ecosystems, increase resilience, develop sound mitigation and adaptation strategies to natural and man-made hazard impacts, and better protect marine ecosystems, among many other uses (EMB 2021). These benefits are linked to the need to protect biodiversity, ensure a healthy Ocean and allow a sustainable use

of marine resources, which rely on biological observations and need further efforts to be fully integrated into the global Ocean observation system (Benedetti-Cecchi et al., 2018). They generate baseline knowledge informing Ocean governance, Ocean economic opportunities, and sustainable development. In situ Ocean observations are also pivotal to improve weather predictions, predict extreme events such as Harmful Algal Blooms, and inform tsunami warning systems, among many others. This mostly publicly funded ocean observing infrastructure generates openly-accessible data as a global public good from which specific information products and knowledge are created to deliver direct and indirect benefits to society as a whole by informing public policy, governance and business decisions following the value chain concept from sensors, through information and knowledge to public benefit.

Figure 3. The value chain of ocean and coastal observation collection, transformation and use (from Smail et al., 2019)

Internationally, evaluating the costs and funding of the observing system is challenging due to differing motivations, running costs, salaries, exchange rates and costing models used across organizations and nations. As stated in the EC’s consultation on Ocean observation ([Ocean observation – sharing responsibility](#)¹), the EU member states currently spend more than €1.5 billion a year in observing the ocean, some of which is funded by the EU and some is to meet the EU legislation.

Although the benefits of Ocean observations are difficult to comprehensively identify and value (OECD, 2019; Rayner et al., 2019), a high benefit-to-cost ratio for investing in Ocean observations has been described in several case studies. The JERICO-NEXT project found a high benefit-to-cost ratio (~5) for the European coastal component of the observing system (Gaughan et al., 2019), in the United Kingdom, the Marine Environmental Data and Information Network (MEDIN) estimated that the benefit of their data services is eight times the cost invested, and a study by Nygård et al (2016) in the Baltic Sea demonstrated that the value of improved information of the status of the sea can be an order of magnitude greater than the associated monitoring costs.

¹ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/12539-Ocean-observation-sharing-responsibility_en

While these studies often use different methodologies, leading to results that are difficult to compare, they still demonstrate a significant positive return on investment.

Considering the above, the need for ocean data and the associated monetary value in obtaining it as well as in the delivered products and services, a critical issue is the quality of the data. Data quality is important because it directly impacts the accuracy and reliability of information used for decision-making and thus it is fair to argue that even small improvements in the quality of the acquired data will have a multiplicative and very significant effect at the other end of the value chain.

1.2 Data quality: the basics

As shown, data quality is a crucial concept of the data value chain, and we propose to have a closer look into it, explaining what data quality underlies in terms of activities and actors.

Data quality has always been a key notion in sciences, essentially related to the validity of measurements, so much so that a specific scientific field has been dedicated to it: metrology (i.e. the science of measurement). Actually, metrology is one of the oldest sciences dating back to ancient civilizations (Fanton, 2019). Taking advantage of its long history and of the progressive globalisation of economy and sciences, metrology has reached a high level of maturity with international harmonization (Fig. 8 in §1.3.1). In 1995, with the publication of the JCGM² 100 “Evaluation of measurement data - Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement” (GUM), the notion of measurement uncertainty became widespread. Measurement uncertainty is defined by the International Vocabulary of Metrology (VIM) as the non-negative parameter characterizing the dispersion of the quantity values being attributed to a measurand. In a word, measurement uncertainty is the doubt that can reasonably be attributed to a value: as so, it embodies data quality. Even though data quality is usually conceptualised as accuracy and reliability of data, technically speaking, data quality is estimated by measurement uncertainty and is supported by measurement traceability (Fig. 4).

² Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology

Figure 4. Traceability concept to the International System of Unit (SI)

However, as indicated, uncertainty, i.e. data quality, is a quite recent concept mastered by the metrology community but not fully comprehended nor used in the oceanographic field. More globally, the same statement applies to all metrology concepts and tools. They are underemployed for different reasons: lack of common knowledge on metrology, very few metrology laboratories fully dedicated to oceanography, high running costs and access costs to metrology facilities, lack of dedicated time for metrology in the oceanographic field.

As explained in the deliverable MINKE consortium D2.4 (2025) and reminded in figure 5 hereafter, data quality needs to be related to expressed requirements and these requirements can change depending on the marine topic addressed.

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \textit{Measure} \pm \textit{Uncertainty}(\textit{Measure}) \\
 \textit{Uncertainty}(\textit{Measure}) \overset{?}{\longleftrightarrow} \textit{Requirement}
 \end{array}$$

Figure 5. What does data quality mean? (Uncertainty = expanded uncertainty)

Data quality depends on several interconnected factors that span the entire data lifecycle, including collection, processing, and dissemination and, the path toward quality data involves numerous actors (Fig. 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Example of activities related to the data quality chain

Figure 7. The Micro, Meso, and Macro Levels of a Big Data Ecosystem (Curry et al., 2016 adapted from Moore, 1996): adaptation to the marine domain

It is thus paramount that the marine community, hand in hand with policy-makers, agrees on data quality requirements in order to implement a suitable metrology. Interconnections between the different stakeholders of the marine data quality chain are crucial links to the accomplishment of data quality. They are discussed in several MINKE consortium deliverables (D4.4, D4.5 and D4.6, 2023, D4.7 and D4.8, 2024, D2.4, D4.9 and D4.10, 2025) and described further in paragraphs 1.3 and 1.4.

At the heart of data quality lies the need for completeness, consistency, transparency, robustness and integrity. These characteristics become more and more fundamental to reach the objective of the development of a digital twin of the ocean which will be strongly dependent on continuous observations from heterogeneous sensors across the world's oceans. Observing systems must be designed to deliver data that can be reliably compared over time and across different regions. Achieving this requires adherence to standardized methods and protocols, regular calibration and validation of instruments, and meticulous documentation of metadata. Such measures ensure that data in datasets are not only accurate but also reproducible, comparable and traceable. As proposed by Wilkinson et al. (2016), all data are recommended to be compliant to the Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable principles to maximize their impact and longevity, as per the EU prevailing requirements for all scientific data. Interoperability is one of the major advances that will enable data comparison among the oceanographic community supported by fundamental metrology bases. Traceability to common references and well-understood and defined measurement uncertainties are the basics of metrology and should be applied by the oceanographic community with the support of the different metrology entities.

In light of all these considerations, the oceanographic field has begun to structure global observing systems which aim at providing the requested data quality for implementing a sound environmental policy. These observing systems advocate interoperability for key measurements identified as Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs).

The way forward in improving the standardization and traceability of Ocean observations is that oceanographers together with metrologists, manufacturers, standardization and accreditation bodies continue advancement in reference methods, definition and dissemination of best calibration practices and data comparisons.

1.3 The current landscape for EOVs and ECVs observations

1.3.1 Ocean Observation and Metrology Networks

The international oceanographic landscape and its interactions with intergovernmental and non-governmental organisations, and the international metrology organization are well described in the deliverable MINKE consortium D1.1 (2022). Figures 8 and 9 summarize them, highlighting entities related to the marine domain (turquoise surround).

Figure 8. International oceanographic organization (non exhaustive). Turquoise surrounded entities are ocean focused

Organisations involved in the oceanographic landscape are numerous and have specific roles to ensure the coordination of Ocean Science and Services.

In the first place, scientists and industrials have organised themselves to tackle scientific and industrial oceanographic challenges through non governmental entities such as, the International Association for the Physical Sciences of the Oceans (IAPSO), the International Association for Biological Oceanography (IABO), the Scientific Committee on Oceanic Research (SCOR) and the Joint Committee on Seawater (JCS).

Then, at the highest intergovernmental level, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) has been established as the leading global authority on the environment. The United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), and its supreme decision-making body, the Conference of the Parties (COP), are in charge of negotiating an agreement to limit dangerous climate change. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) which aims at promoting world peace and security through international cooperation in education, arts, sciences and culture, has, in its turn, set up the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2030) followed, nowadays, by the International Decade of Sciences for Sustainable Development (2024-2033).

In order to ensure harmonization and enhancement of a global observing system, the [Global Ocean Observing System](#) (GOOS) and the [Global Climate Observing System](#) (GCOS) were respectively created in 1991 and 1992. Key measurements were identified as Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and Essential Climate Variables (ECVs). Expert

Panels have been aimed to maintain the definition of those variables, develop and implement observational strategies including sharing a series of [recommendations](#), and guide evaluation of the system. Amongst other, recommendations concern observing approaches (sensor platform, observation frequency, range, etc.), type of measurements (sensors, laboratory analysis, etc.), data management guidelines with quality requirements or current uncertainty capacities.

The European marine networks, organised through projects and European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC), sustained by national oceanographic institutes, are in charge of implementing actions to answer key environmental and marine resources related challenges. Till now, four marine ERICs have been acknowledged to provide sustainable researches and services on topical concerns:

- the European Multidisciplinary Seafloor and water column Observatory ([EMSO](#)), promoting the advance in the knowledge of deep ocean and water column processes, through the monitoring, analysis and dissemination of data retrieved by observatories, or similar instruments, able to ensure long-term repeated observations of the state of the ocean,
- the Integrated Carbon Observation System ([ICOS](#)), producing standardised, high-precision and long-term observations and facilitating research to understand the carbon cycle and to provide necessary information on greenhouse gases,
- the European Marine Biological Resource Centre ([EMBRC](#)), advancing fundamental and applied marine biology and ecology research – while promoting the sustainable blue economy,
- the [Euro-ARGO](#), observing the ocean to better understand and predict its role in the climate system and its health.

Consequently, more and more, high-frequency near-real time marine data have been channelled from oceanographic institutes to European data infrastructures, and thereafter used in a wide range of applications. The integration of observations from EOVs and ECVs have been essential for improving Earth system models, leading, for example, to better predictions of climate trends and variability. These variables have provided critical datasets to support international efforts such as the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC). They have facilitated cross-disciplinary research, enabling a holistic understanding of ocean-climate interactions and their socio-economic impacts. The sustained observation of EOVs and ECVs have also been indispensable to accelerate the sustainable management of ocean resources that is strongly advised and supported by the UNESCO Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission through the “2021-2030 UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development”. High data quality, underpinned by global collaboration and innovation, is essential for transforming observations into actionable insights. The updated requirements by

GCOS and GOOS have provided a robust framework for improving observation networks and ensuring their contributions to global environmental goals.

Figure 9. Synoptic of the “Convention du Mètre” bodies (international metrology organizations). Turquoise surrounded entities are ocean focussed

The metrology international organization is in charge of ensuring worldwide inter-comparability of measurements thanks to their traceability to an agreed international system of units (SI).

This organization relies on the “Metre Convention” (1875) and its different bodies, the General Conference on Weights and Measures (CGPM), the Committee for Weights and Measures (CIPM) and the Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM).

The Mutual Recognition Agreement frames the international equivalence of national standards and national metrology capacities. The whole structure is supported by Consultative Committees arranged by metrology fields, according to the SI. Finally, this international metrology activity is handed over to Regional Metrology Organizations amongst which, the European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET).

This whole structure ensures worldwide data traceability and recognition.

In 2018, EURAMET decided to implement European Metrology Networks (EMNs) in charge of addressing cross-disciplinary metrology questions connected to topical end users’ challenges. Until this date, metrology was mainly governed through SI driven fields (Temperature, Length, Mass, Amount of substance, Time, Electric Current, etc.). These EMNs are composed of National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and Designated

Institutes (DIs). This initiative has led to the setting up of the EMN “Climate and Ocean Observation” (EMN-COO).

During the recent decade, the oceanography and metrology communities have come closer together to meet the growing need for marine measurement quality. The cooperation and coordination of these scientists has led to an increase in data quality and mutual skills, giving rise to the MINKE community. However, an overseeing organisation entirely dedicated to the coordination of the metrology services for marine measurements does not exist yet. Despite their mutual willingness to collaborate for the sake of marine environment, these two different communities have met few opportunities to do so (Salvetat et al., 2019). As shown in figure 10, beyond ad hoc participation to specific projects and entities, very few links have been settled (dotted lines).

Figure 10. Representation of the current international connections between the metrology and oceanographic communities, also featuring manufacturers, civil society and accreditation and standardization bodies (not exhaustive). Inter-field-connections are represented by dotted lines. Traceability pyramids depict traceability paths to the SI or entities related to SI activities. Turquoise surrounded entities are ocean focused

The same analysis applies to society and industry: very few connections exist despite their mutual interest in data quality.

Basic principle of MINKE in supporting Ocean observations is the inclusion and integration of National Metrology Institutes (NMIs) and all actors (ERICs, oceanographic institutes, data aggregators, citizens, manufacturer), which distinctly enhances support to data quality for better interoperability and comparison between observation sites (Fig. 11). Such a task is missing from the current operational ocean

observing value chain. To continue to build and strengthen such a community, which is a necessary tool to bind the oceanographic and metrology sectors, it is necessary to ensure long-term organisation and funding.

Figure 11. MINKE, a bridge between oceanographic observatories and metrology communities to increase the quality of Essential Ocean and Climate Variables

Today, there are altogether around 14 NMIs and designated institutes (DIs) in Europe that have activities supporting marine observation (MINKE consortium D1.1, 2022). These Institutes are members of EURAMET. Four are also partners of MINKE and provide the link between the EMN-COO and the MINKE community. In parallel, quite a few oceanographic calibration laboratories have also been established around Europe in the last decade, a direct result of a widely-acknowledged increasing need for similar infrastructure due to the rapid progress in marine observing technologies, in particular, to the development of automated *in situ* sensors and the widening range of parameters being addressed.

1.3.2 The requirements for EOVs and ECVs observations

The observation requirements for ECVs were recently updated and published by the GCOS (WMO, 2022). These variables are key to characterizing Earth's climate system, including its physical, chemical, and biological components, monitoring climate change impacts on various scales, from global to regional, and supporting climate

adaptation and mitigation strategies by providing reliable data for policymakers and researchers. The updated GCOS guidelines emphasize the need for comprehensive, accurate, and sustained observations of ECVs. These requirements are aligned with the commitments under the Paris Agreement and other international frameworks.

The GOOS has identified EOVs as vital parameters for observing and understanding the ocean’s role in the Earth system. Table 1 lists the latest published EOVs which include physical parameters (such as temperature, salinity, currents, and sea level), biogeochemical variables (amongst which dissolved oxygen, nutrients, and carbon dioxide), and biological and ecosystem variables (including phytoplankton biomass, diversity, and fish abundance).

Physical	Biogeochemical	Biological/Ecosystems
Sea Surface Temperature	Inorganic Carbon	Marine Habitats
Interior Temperature	Total Alkalinity (TA)	Mangrove Cover and composition
Sea Surface salinity	Dissolved Inorganic Carbon (DIC)	Macroalgal Canopy Cover and composition
Interior Salinity	pCO ₂	Hard Coral Cover and Composition
Surface Currents	Nutrients	Plankton
Ekman Currents	Silicate	Zooplankton Diversity
Surface Geostrophic Current	Phosphate	Zooplankton Biomass
Subsurface Currents	Nitrate	Phytoplankton Diversity
Vertical Mixing	Oxygen	Phytoplankton Biomass
Sea Level	Dissolved Oxygen concentration	
Regional Mean Sea Level	Transient Tracers	
Global Mean Sea Level	¹⁴ C	
Sea State	SF ₆	
Ocean Surface Stress	CFC-11	
Ocean Surface heat Flux	CFC-12	
Radiative Heat Flux	Nitrous Oxide N ₂ O	
Sensible heat Flux	Interior Ocean Nitrous Oxide N ₂ O	
Latent Heat Flux	N ₂ O Air-sea flux	
Sea Ice	Ocean Color	
Sea Ice concentration	Chlorophyll-a	
Sea Ice Thickness	Water leaving Radiance	
Sea Ice Drift		
Sea Ice Age		
Sea Ice Temperature		
Sea Ice Surface Albedo		
Snow Depth on sea Ice		

Table 1. List of ECVs for Ocean observations from the GCOS (2022)

Achieving the required observational standards for EOVs and ECVs faces several challenges including gaps in global marine observation networks (particularly in remote and deep-ocean regions), limited funding and resources (affecting the deployment and maintenance of observing infrastructure), data accessibility and harmonization, and interoperability across diverse observing systems. However, advances in technology, such as autonomous observing platforms and satellite remote sensing, are continuously offering more and more opportunities to enhance global coverage and data quality. As technology evolves and scientific understanding deepens, observation methodologies must adapt to incorporate new techniques and address emerging challenges. Flexibility in protocols and openness to innovation allow observing systems to maintain relevance and accuracy in a rapidly changing

world. Mastering and enhancing sensor technologies are also major steps to achieve better data quality and interoperability and require strengthening collaborations with manufacturers.

The lessons learnt from MINKE include the importance of performing Inter Laboratory Comparisons (ILCs) to allow better compliance of measurements with relevant metrology approaches that can guarantee comparability of collected data. Within MINKE, only some of the EOVs, such as absolute salinity, ocean currents, dissolved oxygen, fluorescence, ocean sound and pH_T have been targeted for investigation, and a general lack of common procedures for sensor calibration and validation of the measurements was evidenced for all the chosen parameters (MINKE consortium D2.7, 2025). This lack also extended to the application of available interoperability standards, such as the OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium) Sensor Model Language (SensorML), for handling instrument calibration information within, between and across marine observing networks (deliverables MINKE consortium D3.4, 2024 and D3.5, 2025).

Moreover, considering their metrology, these variables are differentiated by an essential principle which is their traceability to the SI (Fig. 4 and MINKE consortium D2.2, 2023). For some EOVs, traceability to the SI is already routinely provided through NMIs or DIs, and there are related operational services already available but with a need for improved standards for field measurements. For some other EOVs, no SI-traceable standards exist, but the ones proposed are commonly accepted by the user community and considered to be sufficiently fit-for-purpose for the moment. For such standards, long time research and collaborations between metrology and oceanographic communities are required for the strengthening of their traceability. These challenging variables are Salinity, Dissolved Oxygen, pCO_2 , pH_T , (amongst several others) and, of course, biological variables, where standardization and traceability is even more difficult to achieve.

Equally important is the global harmonization of observing efforts. EOVs and ECVs are measured using a wide array of technologies and platforms, ranging from autonomous floats and satellites to ship-based surveys and coastal stations. The integration of these diverse datasets requires interoperability and alignment to common frameworks and standards. Such a harmonization effort is crucial for creating cohesive, large-scale datasets that can inform global oceanic models for climate and resource assessments. Though, due to operational constraints, today's oceanographic observatories are as heterogeneous in their deployment strategies (long/short term, fixed/moving, autonomous/ship-based...) as they are in their methods of ensuring measurement quality (MINKE consortium deliverable D2.4, 2025). The next step to fulfil the ambition of a robust observing system that would feed a global Digital Twin Ocean is to enhance the interoperability of these observing platforms. Collaborative efforts among international organizations, national

programs, and research institutions can also address these challenges, fostering shared guidance of global marine observing networks and efforts.

Several efforts have been made at the European level to propose best practices to measure Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs), and the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS; IOC-UNESCO) by itself contains more than 2000 items on this topic. However, despite the large number of published guidelines, many discrepancies still exist from the standpoints of methods and the repeatability of results, and there is an urgent need for cross comparison of techniques and supporting traceability to recognized standards.

As pointed out by the white paper produced by JPI Oceans (JPI Oceans, 2021), the increasing amount of parameters, technologies and data collected worldwide requires the development of an appropriate and sustainable metrology framework. This document describes the current status of some of the most common parameters in this regard and, specifically, it underlines the need to build a strong metrology framework for oceanographic measurements and to make it an integral part of the marine observing and data management domains. Along the same lines, the Strategy Paper of The European Association of National Metrology Institutes (EURAMET, 2021) calls for building European metrology coordination to provide the necessary quality assurance of marine measurements, ensuring long-term validity and global equivalence.

The extensive work performed in MINKE principally relates to fostering the cooperation between the staff (researchers, and technicians and citizens) dealing with marine data acquisition/quality assessment and metrologists to try and reach a consensus on calibration reference materials and methodologies and harmonized operating practices for sensors (MINKE consortium D2.7, 2025). The absence of standard procedures defined following a metrology approach could impact climatological studies or scientific projection of future ocean scenarios in a significant way. The collaboration between different marine Research Infrastructures (RIs) plays a key role in assuring the completeness of the data sets, particularly at global scales (Hartman et al., 2023), and one of the key aspects of the MINKE project was to foster synergies between similar RI operators and metrology institutes, particularly the NMIs.

MINKE has just initiated the process to create a permanent framework of cooperation between Europe's marine research community and its system of NMIs, but more efforts and resources are needed to educate researchers and technicians to apply metrology approaches based on, for example, the BIPM Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement (GUM) or the ISO/IEC guides. The definition and adoption of common terminology (MINKE consortium D2.5, 2024) will be a crucial step forward if critical technical or methodological issues (as well as reporting and metadata conventions) are to be intelligently addressed. A big open issue was found to be the concept of "uncertainty" that is fundamental in metrology and laboratory analyses,

but that is extremely hard to estimate properly in the field, during oceanographic campaigns, or even after some months of deployment at sea in remote areas (MINKE consortium D2.6, 2025).

1.4 Citizen Sciences and “Accessible-tech”

1.3.1 Citizen Sciences

One of the innovative features of MINKE is the inclusion of the citizen science community in the oceanographic infrastructure, promoting services (metrology support, sensors and platforms) for the involvement of society in scientific data and information production. MINKE may be the support for networking between researchers, the private sector and this community in order to strengthen relationships and help citizen science data providers to achieve required and reachable levels of quality for their data (Fig. 11).

The inclusion of citizen science in the MINKE framework is a positive way to open oceanographic observations and metrology knowledge to non-specialists, providing an integrated perspective on ocean data (Miloslavich, P. et al, 2024).

Volunteer participation addresses one of the extended dimensions of quality proposed in MINKE: Completeness. This dimension has been less considered than data accuracy and data uncertainty, probably because these latter are well defined, with standard methods available for their quantification, whereas “dataset-completeness” is not yet a well-understood or widely-implemented concept and has been regularly quantified only in some specific disciplines (like in demographic studies, where it can be measured as the number of people analysed over the total population of interest). But it is clear that there is a pending challenge to evaluate which are the minimum observations to collect to characterize EOVs and ECVs, at least at the desired scales, following the concept of “Fitness for Purpose”. In this context, data collection based on volunteer participation offer to gather large quantities of experimental data, to a degree impossible to attain by traditional sampling activities.

The White Paper on Citizen Science (Serrano et al., 2014) underlined the future challenge concerning citizen trust in Science and scientific data. Addressing societal reconciliation with political decisions, they highlight the importance of citizen trust in measurement that can potentially affect their lives and economies.

1.3.2 Low-cost, low-tech instruments and metrology

Allowing collaboration between FabLabs, oceanographic and metrologists, MINKE can play a role for the development of marine low-cost and low-tech instrumentation with traceable measurements.

In the era of AI and the Digital Twins, the required volume of data has immensely increased. However, considering the complexity of the ocean with many different processes acting on different spatiotemporal scales, trying to adequately observe is a huge challenge. For some years now, the scientific world has become more and more aware of the necessity of resorting to low-cost technology for marine observation. The new challenge is getting the same information with less resources, in some cases applying accessible-technology schemes. In this quest, metrology becomes crucial for several reasons. It will contribute to ensuring that low-tech instruments provide measurements of the same or, at least, known, quality. It will encourage the refinement of the collected information to permit the demonstration of its quality. And it can also engage in its own low-tech revolution, proposing new low-tech calibration schemes. Metrology will thus be the cornerstone of “Better For Less”. Building appropriate calibration setups is fundamental to characterizing the capabilities of low-tech sensors so that they are well-described with an acceptable quality for measurements, also from the standpoint of traceability.

Nowadays, it seems that low-tech sensors and Citizen Science are increasing in terms of numbers of actors and their different places in the chain between the sensor manufacturer and the measurements “in field”. Even if such citizen engagement is positive in the sense of its implication “for” the planet, maintaining acceptable levels of quality for such measurements still remains a challenge that needs tackling.

2. The basis of MINKE’s EU Research Infrastructure

The values, visions and mission for MINKE’s EU Research Infrastructure (RI) were expressed within the community during an *ad hoc* training course held at the University of Milano-Bicocca in January 2024. The course was specifically tailored for the MINKE infrastructure needs: the consortium had the opportunity to follow a guided process to develop a comprehensive strategy, from identifying such a RI’s mission and identity to building the business model and related strategies (Fig. 12).

Figure 12. Strategy and business plan development process, followed by the training of the University of Bicocca in the *ad hoc* course for the MINKE infrastructure

Considering that the MINKE infrastructure involves communities coming from different fields of knowledge (metrology, ocean and participatory sciences), the integration is a challenge due to different vocabularies, scopes and approaches. Therefore, in order to get MINKE members to share a common vision, the University of Bicocca supported the consortium in the process of identifying the work areas and approaches. The definitions proposed in the framework of the strategy and business plan are at an early stage of development for the MINKE infrastructure (Fig. 13): the training discussions and outcomes have been exploited and wider shared within the MINKE community to collect further opinions. The Future steps will therefore be focused on refining the definitions and finalising the associated details. The following paragraphs indicate the state of development and future steps.

Figure 13. The classification of organisational needs and objectives

2.1 Value

The following information refers to the main results of the *ad hoc* training course of the MINKE consortium for the definition of the baseline of the strategy for the MINKE infrastructure. The agreed Values definition were:

Emphasizes collaboration, transparency, accessibility, reliability, interoperability, legacy, citizen engagement, team diversity, and training

Further to the training, a survey summarizing and sharing the thoughts exchanged at the University of Bicocca was submitted to the wider MINKE community. In this order, partners were asked to answer the question “Values: What is important to us?”. The values quoted at the university of Bicocca were summarized, reshaped and presented as indicated in Table 2.

Values (and Legacy): What is important to us?
QUALITY (traceability, accuracy, completeness, uncertainty, etc.)
DIVERSITY (= inclusion) (of people, knowledge, data, activities)

SHARING (harmonization, complementarity) (of best practices, facilities, data, people, etc.)
FAIR (Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable)
KNOWLEDGE BUILDING (capacity building) (research, training, best practices, intercomparison, expertise, testing)
TRUST (= reliability of data, people, methods, products)
AGILITY & SUSTAINABILITY (of the infra to new methods, parameters, policy)
AWARENESS (Society, policy makers, etc. --> the world)
REGULATION (standardization, accreditation, certification, audit)
TRANSPARENCY (ethical principle)

Table 2. List of the possible MINKE RI values proposed in the MINKE RI survey (extracted from the University of Bicocca training)

Partners were asked to quote the different values marking them 0 (not appreciated), 1 (OK) or 2 (inspiring).

Figure 14 indicates the total scores obtained for each value. 15 participants from 13 partnered institutes (59% of the consortium) expressed their opinion.

Figure 14. Scores of the Values expressed by 13 partners of the MINKE community (59% of the consortium)

The two higher scores correspond to the aspirations of SHARING and TRANSPARENCY.

Still receiving more than 66% of votes, the three lower scores are assigned to AWARENESS, AGILITY & SUSTAINABILITY and, the less agreed one, REGULATION.

All the other values received the same acknowledgment: QUALITY, DIVERSITY, FAIR, KNOWLEDGE BUILDING, TRUST.

A free field was proposed for possible addition but was not used.

2.2 Vision

The following information refers to the main results of the *ad hoc* training course of the MINKE consortium for the definition of the baseline of the strategy for the MINKE infrastructure. The agreed Vision definition is:

Focuses on transitioning from data quality to information quality, aiming to promote impactful research through collaboration and improved data exploitation

The follow-up survey proposed to complete this first approach with some more ideas extracted from the discussions (table 3).

Vision: What future we want to create?
A FUTURE STRUCTURED FOR DATA QUALITY Emerging a network/body/authority/supervisor for marine data quality Integration of data uncertainty and completeness to improve information quality
AWARENESS (of Society, policy makers, ... --> WORLD)
EQUITY Provide quality resources (data, methods, facilities, training, etc.) to all (third countries, every gender, young researchers, etc.)
ENVIRONMENTAL CARING Provide marine data for taking care of our environment without affecting it (low-tech, pertinent measures, etc.)
MARINE KNOWLEDGE ENHANCING Make "a future we want" possible, by enhancing the quality knowledge on ocean and seas life, biogeochemical & physical processes

Table 3. List of possible overarching themes for the MINKE RI Vision proposed in the MINKE RI survey (extracted from the University of Bicocca training)

Figure 15. Scores of the Vision themes expressed by 13 partners of the MINKE community (59% of the consortium)

With maximal scores, the MINKE community expresses once more that priority should be given to structuring the marine landscape for improving data quality and enhancing marine knowledge

The vision of a future based on EQUITY, AWARENESS and ENVIRONMENTAL CARING still obtain more than 66% of agreement.

2.3 Mission

The following information refers to the main results of the *ad hoc* training course of the MINKE consortium for the definition of the baseline of the strategy for the MINKE infrastructure. The agreed Mission definition is:

MINKE provides metrology methods for instrumentation and observation systems. The mission statement highlights the importance of high-quality measurement and data

The Missions of the MINKE RI state its raison d’être: it gathers its final goal, the provided activities and its specific added-values.

Mission: Why do we exist?
To provide improved quality information to support policy decision making answering issues related to (environmental) global changes

Provide different types of services (free and paid) to improve and enhance the way data are exploited by the entire oceanographic community to benefit the environment.
To be a reference in marine metrology

Table 4. List of the possible MINKE RI Missions proposed in the MINKE RI survey (extracted from the University of Bicocca training)

Figure 16. Scores of the Missions expressed by 13 partners of the MINKE community (59% of the consortium)

Finally, this last question, analysed with the previous ones related to values and vision, highlights that a MINKE Research Infrastructure should be proposed as a metrology reference structure in the marine landscape, pooling actors and services, sharing knowledge and best practices with full transparency in order to improve marine data quality and enhance global marine knowledge.

2.4 Strategy Process

The RI strategy aims to improve the quality of decision making, the consistency and unity of coordination and communication, and the performance by setting high aspirations. The cycle of setting aspirations, developing a strategy and incorporating performance feedback is called the strategy process. Figure 17 shows a first draft of the progress scheme of MINKE’s community. As the network is still young, the maturation phase aims at keeping on defining more precisely the strategy, values, missions and vision which will drive the RI in a future phase.

Figure 17. MINKE Strategy process

The research infrastructure community needs to identify a strategy that is consistent and that deals with the realities of the business environment. Every member of the community has to measure its performance and use that information to see if the strategy is working and the aspirations are achievable, and then revise them accordingly.

In these first steps towards defining a strategy during the *ad hoc* training course, the MINKE community identified three fundamental aspects as the basis for a strategy:

- MINKE RI aims to provide services to improve data exploitation for the oceanographic community by means of the enhancement of the quality of data.
- MINKE RI connects observational and metrology communities to advance oceanographic and participatory research.
- MINKE RI supports the connection between research and industry to create higher value, therefore allowing industry positioning.

3. First outlines for a business model

In order to outline the business model, which is at a very early stage, the main strengths and weaknesses of RI MINKE were defined, and key focus areas where more effort should be put in, also with a view to a future and complete business plan, were discussed as well (Fig. 18). Paragraph 3.1 details the key areas members should concentrate on in order to formulate a comprehensive business plan.

Figure 18. Summary of the discussion on the opportunities and challenges within the MINKE infrastructure

3.1 Baseline for the future business plan

The following points highlight the details of the discussion that arose during the *ad hoc* training session. The establishment of the foundations for the definition of a comprehensive business plan should include the resolution of these critical items of the main areas of interest of the MINKE infrastructure listed in two discussion blocks: “Core” and “Sustainability and services framework”.

3.1.1. Core of MINKE Infrastructure

- Coordination and collaboration among institutions
 - Unified approach: Need for better coordination and collaboration among the various independent organisations involved in MINKE as members. This includes facilitating the integration of the entities while preserving their individuality by harmonising methods, sharing resources and aligning objectives.
 - Potential for conflicts: Differences in institutional priorities, capabilities and missions could lead to conflict or inefficiency. There are some concerns about how to address these divergences and ensure effective and smooth cooperation.

- Focus and Priorities for MINKE
 - Focus on innovation: Some members wanted MINKE to push the boundaries of current practices, focusing on innovative approaches and integrating various measurement tools and techniques. They saw this as a way to position MINKE as a leader in the field.
 - Balanced approach: Others suggested a balanced approach, maintaining traditional solid services while gradually incorporating innovative practices. They were concerned about moving too quickly towards new methods without adequate validation and support structures.
- Definition of metrology in the context of MINKE
 - Expanded perspective: Members of the consortium proposed a broader definition of metrology, encompassing a range of instruments and measurements, and adapting to modern needs and technologies, extending beyond traditional laboratory settings.
 - Conservative perspective: Consortium members with a more conservative outlook expressed a preference for adhering to well-established and regulated methods. Concerns were raised that expanding the definition could potentially compromise the integrity and reliability typically associated with metrology.
- Integration of metrology within for the ocean community and new methods
 - Traditional metrology approach: Members of the consortium emphasised the importance of established metrology methods and were cautious about integrating new, less-proven methods, stressing the reliability and precision that traditional metrology offers.
 - Innovative metrology approach: Members of the consortium advocated including low-cost sensors and citizen science initiatives. They argued that these methods could broaden the scope and impact of MINKE by providing more comprehensive data and engaging a wider community but it drives the identification and implementation of new metrology methods.
- Citizen Science and Low-Cost Sensors
 - Pro-Innovation: Members of the consortium emphasised the potential of citizen science and low-cost sensors to enhance data collection and democratise science. Despite the inherent uncertainties, these methods and tools could be integrated effectively to provide valuable data.
 - Scepticism and concerns: Critics were concerned about the accuracy and reliability of data from low-cost sensors and citizen science initiatives. The need

for rigorous validation and calibration to maintain data quality could be a challenge for such methods.

- Data Provenance and Quality Assurance
 - Importance of data provenance: Consensus on the importance of acknowledging the origin of data and ensuring proper accreditation to data producers and providers. This involves establishing methods for tracking data provenance that could ensure the quality and reliability of data sources.
 - Challenges in implementation: Implementing rigorous provenance tracking and quality assurance processes can be resource-intensive. Concerns rose about the feasibility and cost-effectiveness of these measures, especially for low-cost sensors and citizen science data.
- Regulatory and ethical considerations
 - Compliance with regulations: Ensuring compliance with relevant regulations and standards, especially in data management and metrology practices. This includes international standards for data quality and measurement.
 - Ethical considerations: Ethical considerations particularly concerning citizen science and public engagement. Ensuring transparency, informed consent and responsible use of data are important ethical issues that must be addressed.

3.1.2. Sustainability and services framework of MINKE Infrastructure

- Sustainability and long-term vision
 - Formal research infrastructure (ERIC): The transitioning MINKE into a formal research infrastructure, like an ERIC, would provide the necessary structural funding and stability for long-term success. This is essential for sustaining high-quality services and research.
 - Alternative structures: Explore different organizational structures and funding models, including more flexible and potentially less formal arrangements. It is important for adaptability and responsiveness to changing scientific and funding landscapes.
- Funding and resource allocation
 - Securing sustainable funding: Long-term sustainability requires secure and adequate funding, need for structural funding from member states and exploring alternative funding models such as membership fees or partnerships.

- Allocation of resources: How resources are allocated, especially between traditional services and innovative projects. Balancing these needs requires careful planning and prioritisation to support both areas adequately.
- Balancing research and service provision
 - Emphasis on research: the importance of maintaining a strong research focus and using the infrastructure to develop new methods and tools was emphasised. Concerns rose that service provision could divert resources from research.
 - Service-oriented approach: The provision of high-quality services should be a priority as it directly supports the research community and industry. A robust service provision could coexist with ongoing research efforts.
- Service provision and client focus
 - Targeting traditional clients: Focusing on traditional customers, such as researchers and industry professionals, and providing well-established metrology services was a reliable way to ensure quality and relevance.
 - Expanding to new client segments: Extend services to non-traditional clients such as citizen scientists and educational institutions would increase MINKE's impact and relevance, but it is a challenge to meet diverse needs.
- Technological infrastructure and capabilities
 - Investment in technology: Need to invest in advanced technological infrastructure to support high-quality metrology services and innovative research. This includes both hardware (e.g., calibration facilities) and software (e.g., data analysis tools).
 - Keeping pace with technological advances: Staying updated with the latest technological advances and integrating them into MINKE's operations is crucial. However, this is a challenge in terms of training, maintenance, and continuous improvement.
- Impact assessment and evaluation
 - Measuring impact: Assessing the impact of MINKE's initiatives and services is important for continuous improvement and demonstrating value to stakeholders. This involves setting clear metrics and regularly evaluating performance.

- Feedback mechanisms: Establishing robust feedback mechanisms to gather input from users and stakeholders is vital. This helps identify areas for improvement and ensures that services meet the community's needs.
- Educational and training initiatives
 - Capacity building: Education and training initiatives are essential for building capacity within the community. This includes training researchers, technicians, and citizen scientists to ensure high standards in data collection and analysis.
 - Developing training programs: Developing comprehensive and accessible training programs requires resources and expertise. Discussions were held on how to effectively design and implement these programmes to reach a wide audience.

3.2 Services

The effort devoted to marine metrology is growing rapidly in Europe, but the landscape has not been unified or coordinated. The need to begin building a strong metrology framework for oceanographic measurements and making it an integral part of marine observing and data management has been noted by various actors (e.g., [JERICO](#) projects, JPI Oceans Joint Action European Marine Sensor Calibration Network [EMARCALNET](#), EURAMET EMN-COO, GOOS and EuroGOOS).

To set MINKE's long-term strategy in the wider EU and global marine science, and policy implementation space, there is a need to identify and collate activities in the nascent marine metrology sector and understand the requirements of the marine observing community in this respect. To this end, a survey was conducted and a questionnaire was widely distributed to the observing community and associated metrology operators, their opinions and viewpoints were collected and analysed (MINKE consortium D1.2, 2024).

For the main question of the survey as to what the user requirements for MINKE were, 22 possible marine metrology-related services and products that MINKE could offer in the future were listed. The contacted stakeholders were asked to consider whether such services and products were needed, if they were already sufficiently available, and whether MINKE could act as a service provider for them in the future. Overall, most of the proposed services were deemed acceptable.

To analyse the results and better understand which services could be requested most from MINKE, the possible services offered were grouped into seven broad categories based on their type. Figure 19 summarizes the overall feedback regarding the seven service categories discussed below.

Figure 19. Answers to the MINKE Questionnaire on mapping the requirements for a European marine metrology network for the question: “Providing that MINKE establishes a long-term European marine metrology network, what metrology-related services and products should it deliver to the marine communities”. The suggested 22 metrology-related services are pooled in 7 thematic categories. For each category, the average of the number of responses acknowledging the possible role of “MINKE as a service provider in the future” positively is indicated (red circle) together with the minimum and maximum number of replies received for specified individual services. (MINKE consortium D1.2, 2024)

The potential service with the highest ranking was “Connect European marine observing community to global efforts in metrology”. Respondents considered the role of MINKE as a coordinating body for European marine metrology as an opportunity to improve the quality of marine observations. By creating a unified platform, MINKE can connect all actors involved in the process (civil society, academia, industry, government) and reinforce its position and role as the face of marine metrology in Europe.

Second, the results also clearly highlight MINKE's possibility to have a key role in informing, training, and providing guidance on metrology issues in marine Science and Technology, as shown by the high rankings for the services relating to this aspect.

A third group, MINKE’s proposals for somewhat more “operational” metrology-related services at the community level – “Coordination and sharing resources for marine

metrology (people, instruments, facilities)", "Harmonisation of methodologies and procedures", "Development of calibration methodologies and reference materials" and "Standardization of methods" (collectively referred to as "Metrology Coordination" in Fig. 19) – were well-received, too. MINKE can act as a hub to reduce costs and increase value by creating a pan-European network of the region's existing calibration infrastructures and building European capacity by exchanging and transferring know-how both within this network and for the wider marine community through workshops, seminars, and staff exchanges. It can be noted that this third group refers equally to services and research topics.

Fourth, some complementary services" Ad hoc assistance and consultation in metrology issues (on-line and on-site)", "Validation and test of new sensors and methods" and "Provision of tools for uncertainty estimation" (grouped as "Practical Metrology Services" in Fig. 19) were slightly less supported than the more strategic ones mentioned above.

The fifth group of proposed services, relating to training, "Overall metrology training (on-site and on-line)", "Training and education materials for early-career researchers and technical staff" and "Training and education materials for citizen science applications" (grouped as "Provision of Training" in Fig. 19), received slightly less interest.

For the services offering direct access to MINKE infrastructure: "Physical access to laboratory validation and test facilities", "... to laboratory calibration facilities" and "... to field validation and test facilities" (the sixth group, collectively labelled as "Physical Access" in Fig. 19), still 50% of the respondents thought MINKE could contribute to these areas.

After responding to 22 pre-selected services and products, respondents were asked to suggest additional metrology-related services and products that MINKE should provide to the marine observing communities. The summary of the responses received to this open-ended question shows that MINKE, in its coordinating role in marine metrology, will achieve a more rigorous and harmonized framework for carrying out this important activity across Europe. In particular, it was suggested that MINKE should contribute to interlaboratory comparisons for those parameters not already included by other international proficiency test organizers. In addition, after identifying the knowledge gaps in the area, participants suggested that MINKE organize joint regional workshops on sensor calibration and further work and provide calibration standards for oceanography to the metrology community.

Survey concluded that MINKE should establish closer links with industry, and particularly sensor manufacturers, to understand their metrology requirements and improve the uncertainty and traceability information accompanying products. Closer

links with research were also mentioned to increase data availability and reliability. The needs of the satellite community in metrology were also highlighted.

MINKE should work in the context of the EU Marine Observation Landscape in close cooperation with the related research infrastructures and initiatives in terms of services provided. It was underlined that some of the above-mentioned services could be shared with other organizations or should be provided in coordination with other organizations/structures (e.g., EOOS).

Overall, what is clear is that the overarching European strategic coordinating missions are those that MINKE should focus on and try to lead in the future. These need to be accompanied by activities relating to dissemination (e.g., workshops), coordination of metrology-related actions, and provision of training.

For the training services: MINKE network is competent to carry out training services for enhancing:

- metrology skill: traceability issues, calibration procedures, uncertainty calculations, etc. The well-known and understood measurement uncertainty will comfort the oceanographic community with their data and will be a strong channel allowing interoperability between the different sites and instruments for EO data.
- data management related to data quality: integration of metadata with the data (metrology information related to the instrument who provides the data: corrections, uncertainties, calibration coefficients, etc.).
- calibration procedures for low-tech instrumentation with a clear definition of acceptable quality/value of resolution/trueness/precision.

3.3 Research

3.3.1 Using metrology RI to improve data quality of EO data and ECVs

EURAMET (Fig. 10 §1.3.1) coordinates the cooperation of NMIs and DIs in Europe in fields such as research in metrology, traceability of measurements to the SI units, international recognition of national measurement standards and related Calibration and Measurement Capabilities (CMCs). It is also in charge of the implementation of the European metrology research program which aims at promoting metrology research in key areas. The former European metrology research programmes [EMRP](#) and [EMPIR](#), and the current [European Partnership on Metrology](#) have funded up to more than 300 joint research projects so far. Furthermore, EURAMET has established several EMNs to provide single point contact for stakeholders to express their needs for metrology research, reference materials, calibration and other metrology services. In

this context, the European Metrology Network for Climate and Ocean Observation (EMN-COO) was set up. Related needs have been collected in a [Stakeholder Needs Review Report](#) (Wooliams et al., 2021) which, in turn, has been the basis for the [strategic research agenda](#) of the EMN-COO (EURAMET, 2022). Applications for funding within the framework of metrology research programmes, in particular within the European Partnership in Metrology programme, must be closely linked to these documents. The MINKE consortium has provided important input for the preparation of the ocean sections of these key documents through its close collaboration with the EMN-COO in tasks 1.1, 1.2 and 4.1. A roadmap on how to continue the collaboration with the EMN-COO in future has been outlined in deliverable MINKE consortium D4.5. The EMN-COO regularly reviews the strategic research agenda to adapt it to the actual metrology needs in climate and ocean observation. Changes are discussed and approved on an annual basis at the general meeting of the EMN-COO. This structure will enable the MINKE network to channel metrology needs aiming to improve data quality of EOVs into metrology research. Doing so, the MINKE network will take advantage of the metrology RI available at NMIs and DIs, but will also offer oceanographic research facilities for respective metrology research to the benefit of both communities.

3.3.2 Metrology facility innovations

As indicated in §1.3.2, to allow scientists deepen their understanding of the marine ecosystems, instrumental technologies must evolve rapidly. This capacity of innovation is crucial for marine research but requires, in its turn, that marine metrology facilities adapt. Reference methods, reference standards, as well as reference testing facilities must stay at the forefront of technology to ensure that the improved instruments keep on being calibrated to their best capacities.

The subsequent metrology innovations can only be achieved through close cooperation between oceanographic institutes (holding full knowledge of the marine constraints), metrology institutes (mastering SI references) and industry (for their technology and integrating capacities).

Innovation requires not only the ability to emulate within the MINKE community but also the ability to understand and anticipate the needs of the oceanographic community. This last point can be easily fulfilled thanks to the direct links with users and manufacturers that TransNational Access or service activities provide.

3.4 TransNational Access (TNA) and Virtual Access (VA)

MINKE wants to support scientific communities in their access to the identified key Research Infrastructures. Transnational access (TNA) offers the opportunity to have the support from experts to assess measurement uncertainty related to their instruments in metrology facilities.

Figure 20. MINKE TNA, VA & Supporting Facilities

The implementation of Transnational Access (TNA) within a Research Infrastructure context requires a comprehensive approach that addresses economic needs, technical readiness, and administrative preparedness to ensure efficient and high-quality user access. This process demands careful planning across several critical areas.

From an economic perspective, it is essential to account for the operational costs associated with maintaining the facilities. This includes equipment upkeep, the use of specific consumables, and logistical expenses related to deploying and retrieving equipment in the field. Additionally, the costs of providing technical and scientific support to users must be considered, covering both the preparation of their visits and post-access result analysis. In cases where users require physical access, funding for travel, accommodation, and equipment shipment should also be made available. Furthermore, the development and updating of training resources, including workshops and online materials, represent another vital area of investment. To optimize financial resources, sharing infrastructure and leveraging virtual training opportunities can prove effective.

In terms of readiness, the infrastructure must be fully operational and capable of accommodating external users, with compatibility for a wide range of instrumentation and experiments. Administrative processes should also be well-defined, ensuring transparency and efficiency in proposal submission, evaluation, and reporting. Providing clear agreements and terms of access is crucial for maintaining a smooth workflow between users and infrastructure providers. Accessibility for users should be a priority, with comprehensive information about TNA opportunities readily available

through websites and other channels. Virtual access options should be developed to accommodate users with limited mobility or funding, broadening participation.

Finally, technical support plays a pivotal role in the success of TNA. The facility must be equipped to offer high-quality assistance tailored to diverse user needs, including real-time troubleshooting. This requires a skilled team capable of supporting users throughout their projects, from initial setup to data analysis.

The management of TNA within a Research Infrastructure framework requires not only a robust technical and administrative strategy but also dedicated personnel to ensure the success of its operations. It is estimated that at least one Full-Time Equivalent (FTE) is needed to oversee and execute the various tasks involved, given the diversity and complexity of the processes. The dedicated staff is responsible for coordinating and carrying out all activities necessary to provide efficient and transparent access to the facilities. One of the primary responsibilities is the management of calls, which includes drafting and publishing the calls, as well as receiving and registering proposals submitted by users. Following this, the team must handle agreements, which involve formalizing contracts between users, host facilities, and the consortium, clearly defining access conditions, responsibilities, and collaboration terms.

A critical part of the process is the evaluation of proposals, which entails coordinating expert reviewers and ensuring a fair and transparent evaluation process based on predefined criteria such as scientific excellence, European relevance, and potential technological impact. Once access is granted, the team is also responsible for monitoring the progress of the projects, ensuring that the agreed terms are followed, and providing technical and logistical support as needed.

Finally, the team must oversee reporting, which involves collecting and compiling reports from users about their activities and outcomes. This information is essential not only for ensuring compliance with access agreements but also for evaluating the impact of the TNA program and providing feedback to stakeholders, including funding agencies and the European Commission.

The TNA management intranet developed during the MINKE project is a sophisticated platform designed to streamline and enhance the efficiency of processes related to TNA. Its primary purpose is to provide a centralized, user-friendly environment where all aspects of TNA management can be handled seamlessly. This tool was created not only to meet the immediate needs of the project but also to establish a lasting resource for the future of the RI, ensuring its continued success and accessibility.

At its core, the intranet centralizes the management of TNA applications, allowing users to submit proposals and all necessary documentation in a structured and organized manner. By consolidating these functions into a single platform, the

intranet reduces administrative complexity and ensures consistency in handling applications. Users benefit from a clear and straightforward process that minimizes barriers to access, while administrators gain tools that simplify workflows and enhance operational efficiency.

A key feature of the intranet is its real-time tracking capability, which enables users to monitor the status of their applications throughout the process. Whether in the submission, evaluation, or approval stages, users are provided with transparent updates and timelines, fostering trust and engagement. Automated notifications further enhance this experience by keeping both users and administrators informed of important milestones, deadlines, or required actions, thereby reducing the potential for delays or miscommunication.

The intranet also supports evaluators by providing a structured environment for reviewing and scoring applications. This ensures a transparent, fair, and efficient evaluation process that aligns with the principles of equity and scientific merit. Additionally, the platform includes tools for generating detailed reports on TNA activities, such as application statistics, user demographics, and project outcomes. These reporting capabilities are essential for meeting funding agency requirements and evaluating the overall impact of TNA calls.

Beyond its operational features, the intranet includes resources to support users, such as guidelines, FAQs, and step-by-step instructions for navigating the application process. This emphasis on user support reflects the project's commitment to inclusivity and accessibility, ensuring that researchers, regardless of their background or expertise, can fully engage with the opportunities provided by the RI.

One of the intranet's most valuable contributions is its capacity for long-term archiving. By maintaining records of all past applications, agreements, and project outcomes, the intranet creates a comprehensive historical database that can inform future decision-making and policy development. Its ability to integrate with other research infrastructure tools, such as databases and cloud platforms like European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), further enhances its functionality, allowing seamless data sharing and interoperability within the broader RI ecosystem.

Importantly, the TNA management intranet represents a legacy contribution of the MINKE project. It is not merely a tool for the present but a resource designed to endure and evolve with the needs of the RI. By providing a robust, scalable, and efficient platform, the intranet positions the RI as a leader in facilitating high-quality, accessible, and inclusive research. It sets a standard for best practices in TNA management and serves as a model for other projects and infrastructures seeking to implement similar systems. This intranet embodies MINKE's commitment to long-term impact, innovation, and collaboration, ensuring that its vision for marine metrology continues to benefit the scientific community well into the future.

The Zenodo repository for the MINKE project, hosted under the H2020-MINKE community, plays a crucial role in ensuring open access to the knowledge generated during the project. This platform provides a centralized space for storing deliverables, datasets, reports, and other scientific outputs, aligning with the principles of open science. Additionally, by sharing the data generated through the TNA activities on Zenodo, the project actively supports the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) principles. The repository ensures that all datasets are properly curated with metadata, assigned DOIs, and organized in a way that makes them easily discoverable and reusable by the global research community. This commitment to FAIR data practices enhances transparency, fosters collaboration, and ensures the long-term value and usability of the data, contributing significantly to the advancement of marine metrology and its integration into broader scientific efforts. Through Zenodo, MINKE not only preserves its intellectual outputs but also amplifies its impact by making high-quality data and knowledge available for future innovation and policy-making.

Conclusion

Beyond establishing an initial community, the Minke project provided an overview of practices related to marine data quality. A wealth of information was collected regarding the stakeholders involved and the needs expressed, and was the subject of several MINKE consortium deliverables.

This overview has made it possible to begin to develop initial ideas for what a future marine metrology infrastructure could look like. This structure, entirely dedicated to improving the quality of marine data, thus wishes to support the understanding of the marine domain by placing ethics at the forefront of its values through the transparency of its metrology activities, and sharing and opening up its practices towards new solutions.

The model for this structure has yet to be established, but it already enjoys strong support within the marine community. Indeed, the urgency of improving the quality of marine data is becoming increasingly pressing in a deteriorating environmental context. The initial proposals put forward, particularly in terms of training, workshops, and best practices, have garnered the support of interested parties.

However, a more mature catalogue, including activities answering medium- and long-term needs, must be established. The links between the potential multi-sector stakeholders (private, public) of this community also remain to be defined, as do the modalities for sustaining such a structure.

The convergence of a large number of research infrastructures and marine governance bodies in favour of improving the quality of oceanographic data is a decisive factor in favour of developing this MINKE overarching structure for marine metrology.

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